

Introduction

Welcome to the **second edition** of the Diamond OA (OA) Expertise Center's newsletter! We have been hard at work building up our **portfolio of resources** for our target groups, and organizing **events** to bring the Diamond OA community in the Netherlands together. Keep reading to find out more about these activities, and let us know what you think.

The Team ([Bregt](#), [Femke](#), [Juliana](#), [Maria](#), and [Erica](#))

News & Resources

DEVELOPING A DIAMOND OA DISCOVERY KIT

On May 28th, we held the Developing a Diamond Open Access Discovery Kit workshop at SURF in Utrecht. We collaboratively designed a kit to serve as a **practical resource to help navigate, promote, and support Diamond OA publishing** at universities in the Netherlands. As part of this event, we also presented the results of a **survey on Diamond Open Access** in the Netherlands by Lena Ryzhová and Benedetta Siviero (Erasmus University Rotterdam), and a **panel discussion** moderated by [Bregt Lameris](#) (Open Universiteit) with [Catrien Bijleveld](#) (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam), [Zeila Zanolli](#) (Universiteit Utrecht), [Wim Pouw](#) (Tilburg University), and [Markus Stauff](#) (Universiteit van Amsterdam). This event was co-organized with [Chiara Livio](#) (Utrecht University), [Anne van den Maagdenberg](#) (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam), and [Anna van 't Veer](#) (Leiden University). It was made possible by funding from [OSNL](#).

DIAMOND OA BOOK PUBLISHERS LIST

We have published the first version of our curated list of Diamond Open Access book publishers. It highlights **European publishers that do not charge Book Processing Charges (BPCs)** and are, in principle, **open to authors regardless of institutional affiliation**—making them especially relevant for Dutch researchers. The list was compiled by our interns [Lena Ryzhová](#) and [Benedetta Siviero](#) (Erasmus University Rotterdam) through manual research and direct outreach to publishers. It is now available as an Excel file and will be updated quarterly. We welcome input from the community to help us refine and expand it. Explore the list and contact us if you know a Diamond OA book publisher that should be included!

OUR AMBASSADORS

Bert Bakker

Emilia Jarochowska

Junzi Sun

Mihaela Cimpian

Daniel Trotter

Jos Baeten

Wim Pouw

During the first year of the Expertise Centre, it became clear that most activities around Diamond OA focus on publishers and librarians. **Scholars, who are the authors, peer-reviewers and often editors of academic content**, are often not well informed about what Diamond is and why it is important to embrace this non-profit publishing model. To help us fill this gap, we have found **scholars from different disciplines to inform their research communities about Diamond OA**. Learn more about what our ambassadors have to say about Diamond OA [here](#).

APPLYING THE DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS STANDARD

The Diamond OA expertise center started conversations with the **Netherlands University Presses** about the **Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)**, the quality standard for open access publishing. The presses submitted their responses to the **DOAS self-assessment questionnaire** between April-June 2025. The results point towards a potential focus towards strengthening **two core components: 1) editorial management, as well as 2) Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)**. The results also showed differences between presses, as each of them has its own strengths and distinct set up. Further, the sharing of self-assessment results with each other proved to be very helpful to the group in finding alliances. Based on this, the expertise center will also consider ways of supporting knowledge exchange between presses in order for them to reach high quality standards.

DIAMOND OA
Standard

In the Spotlight

- **Authors shocked by unexpected sale of publisher AUP**. Read about what authors and editors at the University of Amsterdam have to say about the Amsterdam University Press' academic book programme being taken over by commercial publisher Taylor and Francis.
- **Open Journals Collective**. Learn more about this collective of libraries and university-based publishers committed to the core values of Diamond OA.
- **EDCH Registry and Forum**. If you are a Diamond OA Publisher or Service Provider, register your organization and be active in the European Diamond community!
- **Diamond OA Recommendations and Guidelines for Institutions, Funders, Sponsors, Donors, and Policymakers**. Download this comprehensive and flexible framework crafted by DIAMAS to support Diamond OA in scholarly publishing.

Please provide your **feedback** on the **Diamond OA Expertise Centre** website by answering **anonymously** to **this survey** (only composed of 8 questions!).

Agenda

- **July 2-4:** LIBER Annual Conference, Lausanne, FR.
- **July 9:** Discover the EDCH Forum & Registry, Online.
- **September 10-12:** ALPSP Annual Conference and Awards, Manchester, UK.
- **September 22-24:** OASPA 2025 Conference, Leuven, BE.
- More events can be found [here](#).

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We welcome any feedback, ideas, or wishes to contribute that will enable us to further improve the newsletter (diamondexpertisecenter@gmail.com). Feel free to send the newsletter to your colleagues who are interested. They can sign up for the mailing list [here](#).

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